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**PARENTAL INVOLVEMENT AS CORRELATE OF ACADEMIC
ACHIEVEMENT: A STUDY OF TEACHER TRAINEES**

Education

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Abstract

Academic achievement is of paramount importance particularly in the present socio-economic and cultural content. It is the activity, which is accomplished especially superior ability, special efforts and great value. It plays significant role in almost all aspects of human life. It has assumed enormous importance in view of its practical value. There are various social, cultural, administrative and financial constraints responsible to effect academic achievement. Measuring academic performance of teacher trainees is challenging since student performance is product of cognitive and non-cognitive constructs which includes socio-economic, psychological and environmental factors. Present paper has been based on the study conducted on teacher trainees. Parental involvement has

been studied by using parental involvement scale by Chopra and Sahoo (2005).The findings reveal that parental involvement has a significant positive impact on the academic achievement of the teacher trainees irrespective to their gender.

Introduction:

Academic Achievement plays a very vital role in life and it is a most important goal of education in the present age of competition. It has been considered as a very significant factor in the attainment of harmonious development of child. Academic achievement is a combination of two words i.e. Academic and achievement. The term ‘academic’ has been derived from the term ‘Academy’. The meaning of which is “a school where special types of instructions are imparted”. The word Academic means any activity or action that is scholastic in nature. It means the amount of knowledge gained by a student in different subjects of study. It encourages the students to work hard and learn more. Achievement is synonymous with the accomplishment or proficiency of performance. The social acknowledgement of a person’s skill, the range and depth of his knowledge or his proficiency on a designated area of learning or behaviour is indicative of the extent of his/her achievement.

Academic achievement is of paramount importance particularly in the present socio-economic and cultural content. It is the activity, which is accomplished

especially superior ability, special efforts and great value. It plays significant role in almost all aspects of human life, as in science and technology, agriculture. It has assumed enormous importance in view of its practical value. It helps in shaping the career of the individual and planning for future education. It forms the main basis of admission and promotion in the class. In the present education setup the examination plays a predominant role in assessing the talent of an individual. There are sorts of examination – daily, weekly, monthly, quarterly, half yearly an annually etc. Academic Achievement is multifaceted phenomenon.

Over the years behavioural scientists have observed that some people have an intense ‘need to achieve’; others, perhaps the majority, do not seem to be as concerned about achievement. People in whom the need for achievement is strong seek to become accomplished in their task performance. Smith and Spence (1983) defined achievement motivation as “task oriented behaviour that allows the individuals performance to be evaluated according to some internally or externally imposed criteria that involves the individual in competing with others, or that otherwise involves some standard of excellence”. According to Atkinson (1966) “achievement motive is conceived as a latest disposition which is manifested in overt striving only when the individual perceives performance as instrumental to a sense of person accomplishment”. Murray

(1938) defined the need for achievement as the motive “to accomplish something difficult, to overcome obstacles and attain a high standard, to excel one’s self, to rival and surpass others, to increase self-regard by the successful exercise of talent”. There are many social, psychological and academic factors which influence academic achievement by one way or another. In the present investigation parental involvement is taken as a social correlate. Maccoby and Martin (1983) defined “Parental involvement is the degree to which parent is committed to his or her role as a parent.” Ryan et al (1992) parental involvement is “parent’s dedication and consider it as a facilitator of both identification and internalization of social values.” Grolnick and Slowiaczek (1994) defined parental involvement as the allocation of resources to the child’s academic endeavours. Henderson (2002) considered parental involvement as a behaviour that promotes interaction with and reflects commitment to the child including among other activities face to face contact, phoning or writing.

A parent is not just a person who brings a child into the world and cares for him during the helpless years of childhood; instead the role of parent is to equip the child with the resources needed to meet the demands of life. Parents’ behaviour towards the children is an important educational foundation on which children’s formal school of learning is built. When parents are involved in their children’s education at home, they

do better in school and when parents are involved in school, children go further in school. It is an established fact that the learning of the child depends upon the fact that how much his/her parents are involved in the academic achievement of the child. The child who has a positive, trusting relationship with his parents is likely to be confident in his interaction with other. Goyal (2008) studied the impact of parental involvement on academic achievement among secondary school students. It was found there was positive and significant relationship between parental involvement and academic achievement. Stevens (2008) in a study conducted at the University of Oregon has suggested that parental intervention can boost education of student at high risk of failure. The researches undertaken in the field highlighted the impact of parental involvement on the academic achievement but the similar studies conducted on teacher trainees are scant.

Rationale of the Study

In the present era of globalization, there is fierce competition in every sphere of life. On academic side, there is no place anywhere for the average and below average students. Excellence in the academic achievement becomes the pre-requisite in each career and every field. So, academicians and educators are in ongoing debate and

searching for strategies of teaching and learning to get the quality teaching which will result into good academic achievement by the students.

Besides the classroom teaching, teaching technology, intelligence quotient of the child, it has been felt that the proper involvement by the parents put a significant impact on academic achievement of their wards. The present study will go a long way to achieve the maximum academic achievement by the students. The findings of this study will be significantly useful for the teacher educators, parents and the society to guide about the relationship between academic achievement and parental involvement of the students. The findings of the study will be helpful to guide the parents that how can they play important role to accelerate the academic achievement of their wards.

Objectives

1. To study the relationship between parental involvement and academic achievement of teacher trainees.
2. To study the relationship between parental involvement and academic achievement of male teacher trainees.
3. To study the relationship between parental involvement and academic achievement of female teacher trainees.

4. To find out the effect of parental involvement on academic achievement of teacher trainees.
5. To find out the effect of parental involvement on academic achievement of male teacher trainees.
6. To find out the effect of parental involvement on academic achievement of female teacher trainees.

Hypotheses

1. There is a significant relationship between parental involvement and academic achievement of teacher trainees.
2. There is a significant relationship between parental involvement and academic achievement of male teacher trainees
3. There is a significant relationship between parental involvement and academic achievement of female teacher trainees
4. There is a significant difference in the academic achievement of the teacher trainees due to high and low level of parental involvement.

5. There is a significant difference in the academic achievement of male teacher trainees due to high and low level of parental involvement.
6. There is a significant difference in the academic achievement of female teacher trainees due to high and low level of parental involvement.

Methodology

The sample has been selected by random method of sampling. 200 teacher trainees were selected from Barnala and Moga district of Punjab. It was further divided into two categories i.e. male and female. For evaluating the academic achievement of the subjects, marks obtained by the teacher trainees in their graduation were taken as the criteria to assess the academic achievement. To study the parental involvement scale by Chopra and Sahu (2005) was used. Data were analysed quantitatively. Descriptive statistics namely mean, S.D. and t-ratio were calculated. To find the relationship Pearson's co-efficient of co-relation was used.

Discussion of the Results

TABLE 1.

Extent of relationship between academic achievement and parental involvement in total sample of Teacher Trainees.

N	Independent Variable	Dependent Variable	Value of 'r' between independent and dependent variable
200	Parental Involvement	Academic Achievement	.467**

****Significant at 0.01 Level**

From the results of table 1 it is found that there is positive and significant correlation between parental involvement and academic achievement of teacher trainees as value of 'r' is significant at 0.01 level ($r=0.467$). It means parental involvement and academic achievement of teacher trainees are closely related to each other. In other words higher the parental involvement of teacher trainees higher the academic achievement of teacher trainees. Thus hypothesis no. 1 that there is a significant relationship between parental involvement and academic achievement of teacher trainees is accepted in the present study. It can be concluded that with the increase in parental involvement of the teacher trainees their academic achievement can be raised.

TABLE 2
**Extent of relationship between academic achievement and parental involvement in Male
Teacher Trainees**

N	Independent variable	Dependent variable	Value of 'r' between independent and dependent variable
100	Parental Involvement	Academic achievement	.721**

** Significant at 0.01 Level

From the results of table 2, it is found that there is a positive significant correlation between parental involvement and academic achievement of male teacher trainees due to significant value of 'r' at 0.01 level ($r = .721$) There is positive association of parental involvement and academic achievement of male teachers trainees. In other words higher the parental involvement higher the academic achievement of teacher trainees irrespective of their gender. Thus hypothesis no. 2 that there is a significant relationship between parental involvement and academic achievement of male teacher trainees is accepted. It can be concluded that with the increase in the parental involvement of the male teacher trainees their academic achievement can be raised.

TABLE 3
**Extent of relationship between academic achievement and parental involvement in Female
Teacher Trainees**

N	Independent variable	Dependent variable	Value of 'r' between independent and dependent variable
100	Parental Involvement	Academic achievement	.510**

** Significant at 0.01 Level

From the results of table 3 it is found that there is a positive correlation between parental involvement and academic achievement of female teacher trainees. And value of correlation coefficient is significant at value 0.01 level ($r = .510$). There is a positive relationship of parental involvement of female teacher trainees with their academic achievement. In other words higher the parental involvement of teacher trainees, higher the academic achievement of teacher trainees whether they are the boys or girls. Thus hypothesis no. 3 that there is a significant relationship between parental involvement and academic achievement of female teacher trainees is accepted in the present study. It can be concluded that to enhance the academic achievement, the parental involvement of the teacher trainees can be enhanced.

TABLE 4
Statistical scores on Academic Achievement of Teacher Trainees due to High and Low Parental Involvement

Dependent Variable	Group of parental Involvement	N	Mean	SD	DF	t-ratio
Academic Achievement	High parental involvement	62	62.43	30.68	103	3.14**
	Low parental involvement	43	49.65	7.46		

**Significant at 0.01 Level

Table 4 shows that mean scores of academic achievement of teacher trainees

whose parental involvement is high is 62.43, SD is 30.68, while the mean score of academic achievement of teacher trainees whose parental involvement is low is 49.65, S.D. is 7.46 and t-value is 3.14. Significant difference is obtained in the academic achievement of teacher trainees due to high and low level of parental involvement as t-value is found to be significant at 0.01 level ($t=3.14$). Therefore as per the results of the present study academic achievement of teacher trainees is rigorously influenced by the parental involvement. Mean scores of teacher trainees on the variable of academic achievement show that academic achievement of teacher trainees who have high level of parental involvement is higher as compared to the teacher trainees who have low level of parental involvement.

TABLE 5

Value of Mean, S.D. and t-ratio to Locate Difference in the Academic Achievement of Male Teacher Trainees due to High Parental Involvement and Low Parental Involvement

Dependent Variable	Group of parental Involvement	N	Mean	SD	DF	t-ratio
Academic Achievement	High parental involvement	30	61.7	31.28	55	2.01*
	Low parental involvement	27	49.8	7.90		

***Significant at 0.05 Level**

The mean score of academic achievement of male teacher trainees whose

parental involvement is high is 61.7, SD is 31.28 while the mean scores of academic achievement of male teacher trainees whose parental involvement is low is 49.81, SD is 7.90, and t-ratio is 2.01. Significant difference is obtained in the academic achievement of male teacher trainees due to high and low level of parental involvement as t-value is found to be significant at 0.05 level (t=2.01)

The reason may be due to the fact that with involvement of parents, children cannot indulge themselves in negative activities. Parents encourage them to do right type of activities and work hard. So high parental involvement is an important factor in increasing the academic achievement of teacher trainees.

Thus hypothesis no.5, that there is a significant difference in the academic achievement of male teacher trainees due to high and low level of parental involvement is accepted in the present study.

TABLE 6

Values of Mean S.D. and t-ratio to Locate Differences in the Academic Achievement of Female Teacher Trainees due to High Parental Involvement and Low Parental Involvement

Dependent Variable	Group of parental Involvement	N	Mean	SD	DF	t-ratio
Academic Achievement	High parental involvement	32	63.125	29.80	46	2.40*
	Low parental involvement	16	49.375	6.63		

***Significant at 0.05 Level**

The mean score of academic achievement of female teacher trainees whose parental involvement is high is 63.12 and SD is 29.80 while the mean scores on

academic achievement of female teacher trainees whose parental involvement is low is 49.37, SD is 6.63 and t-ratio is 2.49. Significant difference is obtained in the academic achievement of female teacher trainees due to high and low level of parental involvement as t-value is found to be significant at 0.05 level ($t=2.49$)

The reason may be due to the fact that girls are more sensitive and sincere by nature. Parents adopt practical way of life and do the things themselves and the girls immediately act upon and work hard. Hence, parental involvement enhances the academic achievement of girls.

Thus the Hypothesis no. 6, that there is a significant difference in the academic achievement of female teachers trainees. Due to high and low level of parental involvement is accepted in the present study.

Educational Implications

The present study will be significant in the direction to generate the awareness regarding the impact of parental involvement in academic achievement of teacher trainees. The educational college authorities and education department must devise certain programmes to motivate the parents and also provide opportunities for the parents to involve in the educational activities by organizing parent-teacher associations

and holding parent – teacher meetings regularly so that they can realize the importance of education and guide the children to improve their achievement. Findings of the present study reveal that there is significant positive relationship between parental involvement and academic achievement. From this, it may be concluded that good parental involvement leads to higher academic achievement. Therefore, colleges and authorities must try to involve the parents in the college activities, thereby; it helps in improving academic achievement among teacher trainees.

There is a significant difference in the academic achievement of teacher trainees with high and low level of parental involvement. Therefore we have to guide the parents of low achievers to take active involvement in the education of their children by this they may be able to improve the academic achievement of low achievers. In dual earner families, parents should talk to their children to understand their psychological needs and also to help them in their studies and choosing their career. This will help a lot to understand them and to solve their problems. The government and authorities should pay due attention towards the educational colleges. The facilities and infrastructure of the educational colleges should be made liberally.

Research in any branch of human knowledge is never a closed book. There is

always persisted need of finding solutions to new problems and testing the variety at the solution to the other problems. The present study opens up certain avenues for further research. The present study was limited to a small sample of 200 students. It is suggested that large sample can be undertaken. The study of the same nature can be undertaken for different districts of states. The study can be undertaken for schools and universities students. The parental involvement can be studied by using its various dimensions. The study of academic achievement of male and female in relation to parental involvement can be undertaken by taking different age groups and using other methods and tools.

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